

Wind Engine

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Abstract:- One of the main reason for the low mileage of EV's is the drag due to air resistance. However through "wind engine" project we will be able to harness this disadvantage to fuel our vehicle.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this modern era, transportation plays a key role in our lives. This transportation contributes about 29% towards the overall pollution. The only solution to this is using a suitable renewable alternative i.e. This project of wind engine mainly focuses on providing energy from one main drawback EV's that is affecting their success.

II. WIND ENGINE

The word perpetual means endless. In the same way this engine is created to provide endless amount of energy without harnessing any source of external energy or it can also be called as free energy. This engine produces energy mainly on the principle of magnetic repulsion. However it does require the following setup to produce the energy.

A. Engine Model

- Since there has to be a sufficient energy yield to power the vehicle the engine model plays a key role in it.
- As these perpetual engines are aimed to run endlessly its arrangement is very important.
- The only efficient engine for this is a horizontal engine.
- In this model of engine, the pistons and cylinders are placed opposite to each other.
- This ensures the long life of the engine and also efficient production of energy.

B. Framework

- An important factor that has to be taken into consideration is the total area occupied by the whole setup.
- The maximum capacity of the engine area of the vehicle to fix the whole setup is 20*25*45inches.
- The power source is designed with a pair of movable piston where the electricity is generated.
- The generated power is sent to inverter for power regulation.
- The power from inverter is then sent to power control unit which later distributes it to battery and other power minor consumers (like AC, headlight etc...).

C. Generator

- Considering the space and amount power required the generator must be able to produce efficient amount of energy.

The power is generated from two sources: One from directly from the cylinders as they are well coiled. Other from an external generator connected to the shaft.

- Since the power is generated from two sources there would be sufficient power for the vehicle throughout the journey.
- In case if the energy production is still insufficient extra cylinders can be added to produce more energy.

III. WEAR AND TEAR

Since these pistons don't work on any fuel they don't produce any heat inside the cylinder. Only part where energy is lost due to friction is axial which can also be reduced by lubricating. The overall heat produced may decrease the life of the generator, this problem can be solved by using coolants. Due to this overall cost of maintenance is very low.

IV. STABILITY

Though this engine is able to run endlessly it has to be stopped at some point of time. In order to stop it a stop motor is used to stabilize the blades and also a lever made of copper is used at the ends of the cylinder to stop the piston from further movement by suppressing their forces.

V. SPECIAL FEATURES

- It has an Output range of about 80.3kwh on average (combining both power source).
- The expected lifetime of this engine is estimated to be around 40-50 years.
- Due to its added features, the cost of maintenance and repair is also low.
- The whole setup must be covered with copper to minimize the external attraction and repulsion.

VI. CONCLUSION

The project of wind engine is mainly aimed to provide energy to the electric vehicles from where it is being lost. By this method we can improve the market scale in establishing EV's. The increase in usage of EV would eventually decrease global warming. But still until the desirable wind speed required to activate the turbine is reached, we can only rely on the battery of the car.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

My idea for the creation of this project was mainly inspired by world's genius Mr. Nikola Tesla. His thrust to create more methods to harvest electricity non-renewably inspired me in doing this.

REQUEST TO FELLOW READERS

While going through this paper if you do find anything skeptical don't hesitate to reach me. Both your doubts and ideas are appreciated. Your help in initiating this protocol would definitely be welcomed.

REFERENCES

The following websites were used were used as references for this project of Road Median Turbine.

- [1].<https://www.elprocus.com/different-types-of-solenoid-working-applications/>
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